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Macro-environmental Forces And Market Performances Of Small And Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Yenagoa

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ABSTRACT

This study examines macro-environmental forces and market performances of SMEs in Yenagoa. A descriptive and survey research design was used to carrying out the research work with a sample of 130 respondents. The primary source of data was used, which includes the design of questionnaires and administration on the field to get raw information. Four hypotheses were tested to determine relationship between independent and dependent variables. The study concluded that external business environment has positive effect on performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). The study therefore recommended that owners/managers of SMEs should have positive perception towards economic environment as customers today tend to have control of the economic environment in order to increase their performance. Finally, the study recommended that prompt knowledge of new technologies should be adapted by the owners/managers of SMEs as it will go a long way in enhancing the quality of goods and services.

Keywords: Macro-environmental forces, Market performance, Small and Medium Enterprises, Profitability

INTRODUCTION

Every company operates within the internal and external environments of business. The internal environments are within a firm such that the prevailing factors are most times very subject to the control of the managers. The external environment has to do with the larger business environments in which a firm operates; and the factors therein are not subject to the control of the managers. The factors in the external environment not subject to the control of a manager generally can be regarded as macro environmental forces. Marketing activities are the business strategies adopted in making products available for the satisfaction of consumer. Edna and Eboh (2011) viewed marketing performance as everything needed to get a product off the business premises and pass it to the final consumer for profitable exchange. Ade (2014) stated that marketing consists of individual and

organizational activities aimed at facilitating and expediting exchanges within a set of dynamic environmental forces.

Environmental forces are the totality of forces and institutions that are external and potentially relevant to the firm. Baker (2004) referred to environmental forces as the ultimate constraint upon the firm's strategy. Also, Odigbo (2011) expressed that business environment means forces that influence business objectives, functioning, strategies and the entire performance of organization in an area. However, environmental forces could be termed as those elements that are beyond the control of the business and which must be reckoned with in their marketing planning activities. These elements could be classified as controllable and uncontrollable forces.

Controllable forces of marketing environment are product, price, promotion and place and they are referred to as micro environmental forces. Whereas, demographic forces, economic conditions, technological change, social/cultural change, legal/political forces and competition constitute the uncontrollable elements of marketing environment which could be regarded as macro environmental forces (Osuala, 2013). According to Odigbo (2011) macro environment refers to factors that are largely outside the control and influence of a business and that can potentially have positive and/or negative impact on the business. In view of this, the uncontrollable forces are those factors that require proper and adequate monitoring by the business for better and efficient maintenance of the business activities.

Macro environments are demographic, economic conditions, social and cultural changes, technological changes, legal and political forces and forces of competition. Ade (2014) explained that demography as the country's population and its geographical dispersion of people is important to the marketer in selecting target market, location of plants and warehouses and selection of distributors. This shows that people make market and their tastes and preferences determine what to produce at a particular point in time. Also, Anyanwu (2016) indicated that economy has tremendous effects on the marketers' decisions because it determines the buying decisions of the buyers. If the economy is healthy, business activities will be smooth and all aspects of business including marketing will be very active and during the recession business activities are at their lowest and marketing is mostly affected in any society. Moreso, societal reaction to a new product could be instrumental to its success and at the same time could be fatal. Consequently, the businesses monitor social changes and try to adapt to change by keeping in touch with the business environment.

Changes in technology constitute a great challenge to the survival of business marketing activities. Ade (2014) stated that technological changes and innovations and discoveries affect peoples' lives and consumption patterns dramatically. As new products are introduced, old ones are withdrawn. It is by virtue of these changes in technology that cause a shift in the consumer's tastes and preferences. This implies that changes in technology constitute challenges on the business to have a better control of their activities by shifting their resources towards the technological advancement as to meet up with the modern way of production and distribution of goods and services.

Government in other hand regulates business activities by enacting laws that influence the conduct of business in any economy. Osuala (2013) stated that in the civilized world political action sets the legal boundaries for business and other forms of activity. In addition, another form of forces that influence marketing activities of business is the force of competition among the business operators. Business organization irrespective of their area of operation, experience and academic background need to be aware of the changes that constantly occur in the business environment because the success or survival of business enterprise can be determined by how knowledgeable and cognizant business

operators are on marketing environmental forces which are regarded as a pivot upon which profitable marketing activities rotate.

Statement of Research Problem

Researches on the relationship between macro environmental forces and firm's marketing performance have been ongoing in advanced countries of the world with little or no research in developing countries of the world such as Nigeria. It is this existing gap that informed the rationale behind this study. Several of the existing literatures identified various problems facing organization in a globalised environment such as difficulty in facing recession, low productivity, lack of managerial capabilities, lack of financing among others. These problems cause business organization not to perform effectively. It is on this note that the study seek to investigate the relationship between macro-environmental forces and market performance in Yenagoa.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the relationship between macro environmental forces and market performance.

Other specific objectives are to:

- i. Investigate the relationship between political environment and firm's profitability
- ii. Find out the influence of economic environment on firm's profitability
- iii. Determine the effectiveness of social cultural environment on firm's profitability

Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between political environment and firm's profitability?
- ii. How does economic environment influences firm's profitability?
- iii. To what extent does social cultural environment affect firm's profitability?

Research Hypotheses

- H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between political environment and firm's profitability
H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Economic environment and firm's profitability
H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between Social cultural environment and firm's profitability

METHODOLOGY

In this research work, descriptive technique was used where survey research design was adopted. This was done by selecting a sample from the total population. The information collected was analyzed and use to make decisions and generalization about the characteristics of the population from which the sample was selected. A population consists of all elements-individuals, items or objects whose characteristics are being studied. The total population of the study is two hundred and fifty "250" (SMEs) owners in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state.

The sampling method used was probability where simple random sampling technique was used. This was done by taking a sample of the population in a way that each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected. The sample size of this research is 130 staff and customers of (SMEs) owners in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state.

In this research work, information or data was obtained from both primary and secondary source of data collection. Primary data was obtained through administration of questionnaire to the respondents while secondary data was obtained by reviewing relevant journal, past work of other researchers, textbooks, and internet.

To validate the instrument of this research work, content and face validity was used. This was done by making sure that all the questions asked in the questionnaire fully exhaust all the research questions and hypothesis and also submitted to the supervisor who vets the content objectively to determine their relevance and level of coverage.

Test-Retest method was used for reliability. This was done by applying the same research instrument on the same sample twice under similar conditions but at different times. The correlation coefficient between the results was calculated using Pearson’s correlation coefficient formula.

In this research work quantitative method of data analysis was adopted. This was done by transforming what is collected into numerical data to make sense of the responses by organizing, summarizing and presenting it on tables. Information obtained was presented using statistical package for solution service (SPSS) and the hypothesis formulated was analyzed and tested using correlation method.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This chapter covers the analysis and the results of information gathered from research field. It describes the process of analysis of the data using information gathered in the administered questionnaires. Data collected becomes meaningful to the users and the researchers when they are well analyzed. The research questions, study objectives and hypothesis formulated in chapter one were tested and answers were provided in this chapter.

Response rate

One hundred and thirty (130) questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, out of 130 questionnaires distributed, Only 96 were duly filled and returned, making a response rate of 74%.

Section A: Bio Data of the Respondents

Table 1: Age Distribution of Respondents

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
18-25Years	15	15.6
26-35Years	18	18.8
36-45Years	51	53.1
46Years and above	12	12.5
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

Table above shows that (15) 15.6% of the respondents are between the age of 18-25 years, (18) 18.8% are within the age of 26-35 years, (51) 53.1% are within the age of 36-45 years, (12) 12.5% are within the age 46 years and above. This can be translated that majority of the respondents fall between the age 36-45 years.

Table 2: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Male	62	64.6
Female	34	35.4
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (62) representing 66.6% of the respondents were male, while (34) representing 35.4% of the respondents were female.

This can be translated that there are more male than female constituting the sample respondents.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Marital Status

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Single	19	19.8
Married	73	76.0
Divorce	4	4.2
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that 19 respondents represents 19.8% were single, 73 respondents represents 76.0% are married while 4 respondents represent 4.2% are divorced. This can be translated that majority of the respondents are married.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by Educational Qualification

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
O'level	6	6.3
ND/NCE	10	10.4
HND/BSC	59	61.5
MS.c/MBA	15	15.6
Ph.D	4	4.2
Others	2	2.1
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above indicates that (6) 6.3 % were SSCE holder, (10) 10.4% were ND/NCE holder, (59) 61.5% were HND/BCS holders, (15) 15.6% were MS.c/MBA holders, (4) 4.4% were Ph.D holders, while (2) 2.1% of the respondents choose others. From this, we can say that majority of the respondents is educated to an acceptable extent. Thus, they are able to comprehend and provide proper answers to the questionnaire.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents by Work Experience

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
1-10Years	23	24.0
11-15Years	52	54.2
16-20Years	12	12.5
21Years and above	9	9.4
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (23) 24.0% of the respondents have 1-10years work experience, (52) 54.2% have 11-15years, (12) 12.5% have 16-20years, while (9) 9.4% of the respondents have 21years and above work experience. This can be translated that majority of the respondents have 11-15years work experience.

Section B: Analysis of Research Questions

Table 6: Quality of goods to be produced is been determine by the environment

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	28	29.2
Agree	32	33.3
Disagree	24	25.0
Strongly Disagree	12	12.5
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (28) 29.2% of respondents strongly agree that Quality of goods to be produced is been determine by the environment, (32) 33.3% agree, (24) 25.0% disagree, while (12) 12.5% strongly disagree. This suggests that majority of the respondents agree that Quality of goods to be produced is been determine by

the environment.

Table 7: The demand for goods and services in the environment is mostly determine by exchange rate

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	15	15.6
Agree	29	30.2
Disagree	32	33.3
Strongly Disagree	20	20.8
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (15) 15.6% of respondents strongly agree that The demand for goods and services in the environment is mostly determine by exchange rate, (29) 30.2% agree, (32) 33.3% disagree, while (20) 20.8% strongly disagree. This suggests that majority of the respondents disagree that The demand for goods and services in the environment is mostly determine by exchange rate.

Table 8: Business growth is determined by economic policies put in place by government

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	47	49.0
Agree	25	26.0
Disagree	17	17.7
Strongly Disagree	7	7.3
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (47) 49.0% of respondents strongly agree that Business growth is determined by economic policies put in place by government, (25) 26.0% agree, (17) 17.7% disagree, while (7) 7.3% strongly disagree. This suggests that majority of the respondents strongly agree that Business growth is determined by economic policies put in place by government.

Table 9: Business owners allow employees time for religious activities

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	38	39.6
Agree	19	19.8
Disagree	25	26.0
Strongly Disagree	14	14.6
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (38) 39.6% of respondents strongly agree that Business owners allow employees time for religious activities, (19) 19.8% agree, (25) 26.0% disagree, while (14) 14.6% strongly disagree. This suggests that majority of the respondents strongly agree that Business owners allow employees time for religious activities.

Table 10: New technological product brings increase in sales

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	33	34.4
Agree	7	7.3
Disagree	14	14.6
Strongly Disagree	19	19.8
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (33) 34.4% of respondents strongly agree that New technological product brings increase in sales, (7) 7.3% agree, (14) 14.6% disagree, while (19) 19.8% strongly disagree.

This suggests that majority of the respondents strongly agree that New technological product brings increase in sales.

Table 11: Access to internet increase customer patronage

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	48	50.0
Agree	33	34.4
Disagree	9	9.4
Strongly Disagree	6	6.3
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (48) 50.0% of respondents strongly agree that Access to internet increase customer patronage, (33) 34.4% agree, (9) 9.4% disagree, while (6) 6.3% strongly disagree. This suggests that majority of the respondents strongly agree that Access to internet increase customer patronage.

Table 12: Low level of education affects business performance

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	53	55.2
Agree	24	25.0
Disagree	12	12.5
Strongly Disagree	7	7.3
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (53) 55.2% of respondents strongly agree that Low level of education affects business performance, (24) 25.0% agree, (12) 12.5% disagree, while (7) 7.3% strongly disagree. This suggests that majority of the respondents strongly agree that Low level of education affects business performance.

Table 13: Age of the target market has influence on the type of goods to be produced

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	26	27.1
Agree	50	52.1
Disagree	12	12.5
Strongly Disagree	8	8.3
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (26) 27.1% of respondents strongly agree that Age of the target market has influence on the type of goods to be produced, (50) 52.1% agree, (12) 12.5% disagree, while (8) 8.3% strongly disagree. This suggests that majority of the respondents agree that Age of the target market has influence on the type of goods to be produced.

Table 14: Educational background has influence on the tastes and performance of the customer

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	55	57.3
Agree	24	25.0
Disagree	14	14.6
Strongly Disagree	3	3.1
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (55) 57.3% of respondents strongly agree that Educational background has influence on the tastes and performance of the customer, (24) 25.0% agree, (14) 14.6% disagree, while (3) 3.1% strongly disagree. This suggests that majority of the respondents strongly agree that Educational background has influence on the tastes and performance of the customer.

Table 15: Economic forces has influence on business performance

Response variable	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	25	26.0
Agree	43	44.8
Disagree	17	17.7
Strongly Disagree	11	11.5
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2021.

The table above shows that (25) 26.0% of respondents strongly agree that Economic forces has influence on business performance, (43) 44.8% agree, (17) 17.7% disagree, while (11) 11.5% strongly disagree. This suggests that majority of the respondents agree that Economic forces has influence on business performance.

Test Of Hypothesis

Table 16: Correlations (hypothesis One).

H01: There is no relationship between macro environmental forces and market performance

Correlations

		Macro environmental forces	Market performance
Macro environmental forces	Pearson Correlation	1	.822**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	106	106
Market performance	Pearson Correlation	.822**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	106	106

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Decision rule: Reject H0 if Pearson correlation coefficient is less than 1, Accept H0 and reject H1 if the calculated value is equal to 1 or greater than 1 at (0.01) significant level (2-tailed).

Conclusion: Since the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.822** and the P value is 0.000. This shows that P value < 0.01. Conclusion is that there is relationship between macro environmental forces and market performance.

Hypothesis Two:

Table: Correlations (hypothesis Two).

H02: There is no relationship between political environment and customer satisfaction

Correlations

		political environment	customer satisfaction
political environment	Pearson Correlation	1	.774**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	106	106
customer satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.774**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	106	106

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Decision rule: Reject H0 if Pearson correlation coefficient is less than 1, Accept H0 and reject H1 if the calculated value is equal to 1 or greater than 1 at (0.01) significant level (2-tailed).

Conclusion: Since the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.774** and the P value is 0.000. This shows that P value < 0.01. Conclusion is that there is relationship between political environment and customer satisfaction.

Hypothesis Three:

Table: Correlations (hypothesis Three).

H02: Economic environment does not influence customer satisfaction

Correlations

		Economic environment	customer satisfaction
Economic environment	Pearson Correlation	1	.685**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	106	106
customer satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.685**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	106	106

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Decision rule: Reject H0 if Pearson correlation coefficient is less than 1, Accept H0 and reject H1 if the calculated value is equal to 1 or greater than 1 at (0.01) significant level (2-tailed).

Conclusion: Since the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.685** and the P value is 0.000. This shows that P value < 0.01. Conclusion is that Economic environment influence customer satisfaction.

Hypothesis Four:

Table: Correlations (hypothesis Four).

H02: Social cultural environment does not affect customer satisfaction

Correlations

		Social cultural environment	customer satisfaction
Social cultural environment	Pearson Correlation	1	.841**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	106	106
customer satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.841**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	106	106

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Decision rule: Reject H₀ if Pearson correlation coefficient is less than 1, Accept H₀ and reject H₁ if the calculated value is equal to 1 or greater than 1 at (0.01) significant level (2-tailed).

Conclusion: Since the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.841** and the P value is 0.000. This shows that P value < 0.01. Conclusion is that Social cultural environment affect customer satisfaction.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result analyzed using the Statistical Package for Solution Service (SPSS) with the Pearson correlation method shows that there is significant relationship between the hypotheses as presented above.

The first hypothesis shows a correlation between the independent variable and dependent variable. It shows that there is relationship between macro environmental forces and market performance. The study revealed that macro-environmental forces and market performance were positively and significantly related. The findings on macro-environmental forces were in conformity with the opinion of Odia and Odia (2013) who confirmed through the result of their studies that macro-environmental forces have positive effect on market performance.

The second hypothesis shows a correlation between the independent and dependent variable. It shows that there is relationship between political environment and customer satisfaction. The third hypothesis shows a correlation between the independent and dependent variable. It shows that economic environment influence customer satisfaction. It shows that macro-environmental forces affects market performance of Small and medium enterprises (SMEs)

SUMMARY

This study carefully examines relationship between macro-environmental forces and market performance in Yenagoa. Various literature where reviewed and discussed in chapter two to further explain the subject matter with the consultation of relevant concept and theories. In Chapter three research methodologies applied in generating relevant data and how some data is analyzed was carefully discussed.

However, in chapter four, data gathered were presented and analyze using statistical package for solution service (SPSS) which was presented with the aid of tables for easy interpretation and understanding. Therefore, the hypotheses were tested using correlation method in order to establish relationship existing between the variables.

CONCLUSION

Business operators require proper and adequate awareness on macro-environmental forces in order to adopt marketing skills which includes marketing research, environmental scanning and analysis, forecasting, market segmentation, marketing planning and control for better and effective market environmental analysis in order to adopt marketing skills required for better and effective business operations. It is hoped that if business operators are well aware of the influence of these macro-environmental forces and proper steps are taken while planning it, will go a long way in helping business to be effective in achieving the objectives for which it is being established most especially in the area of profit maximization and job creation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Seminars and workshops should be organized annually by business operators for improving and updating their knowledge about the significant of macro-environmental forces.
- ii. Relevant information should be given by the government through relevant agencies to the business operators the changes in the business laws which may have significant effect on the business activities.
- iii. Qualified and well grounded business administrators who can handle successfully the risk involved in the business environment should be employed by business operators.
- iv. Business operators should familiar themselves to the relevant business materials like newspaper, magazine, business books and internet materials.

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